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The Financial Management of Waste in the Municipality of Adelfia

Waste taxes increased by 128.45% between 2010 and 2022

Below we consider the waste tax policies of the municipality of Adelfia in the period between 2010 and 2022. We consider both receipts and payments in their evolution. The data is acquired using the Siope database in collaboration between the Bank of Italy and the State General Accounting Office. It should be considered that between 2010 and 2016 the tax connected to waste management was indicated as TARES which from 2016 onwards was replaced by the TARI. The two tributes were considered in succession. In addition, we have also considered the Payments section as well. These are the expenses that the municipality of Adelfia had to guarantee the waste disposal service to the population. Also in this case, in the succession of financial statements between 2010 and 2022, we notice changes in the names of the accounting items. However, it must be understood that these items, albeit modified, are placed in continuity. In fact, they are intended to represent the financial outlays of the municipality of Adelfia incurred for waste management.

The collections from waste management of the municipality of Adelfia between 2010 and 2022. Between 2010 and 2011 the collections from TARES of the municipality of Adelfia increased from € 1,269,713.95 to a value of 1,698,989.87 € or a value equal to € 429,275.92 equal to +33.81%. Between 2011 and 2012 revenues from TARES grew further up to €1,909,046.07, i.e. +210,056.20 € equal to +12.36%. In 2013, tax revenues from Tares grew further up to a value of €1,960,787.16, i.e. a growth of €51,741.09, equal to 2.71%. Between 2013 and 2014, the value of the TARES revenue of the municipality of Adelfia grew by a further 300,000 euros, equal to 15%, up to 2,261,393.46 euros. The period between 2014 and 2015 the TARES decreased until it reached a value of €1,333,826.42, equal to a reduction of € -927,567.04, equal to -41.02%: However, between 2015 and 2016, the first year of application of the TARI, the value of waste taxes has grown further up to a value of 2.38 million euros equal to a growth of 1 million euros equivalent to +78.58%. Between 2016 and 2017 there was a reduction in the value of taxes for the TARI or a decrease of -120 thousand euros equal to -5.08%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the TARI receipts of the municipality of Adelfia decreased further reaching € 2,128,896.29 or a reduction of € -132,128.12 equal to -5.84%. Between 2018 and 2019, the TARI revenue of the municipality of Adelfia grew by € +550,565.45 or +25.86%. In the transition between 2019 and 2020, tax revenues from TARI decreased by € -173,818.73 or -6.49%, reaching € 2,505,643.01. Between 2020 and 2021, tax revenues from TARI increased by €125,256.92 or by an amount equal to 5.00% up to an amount of €2.6 million. Between 2021 and 2022 the value of tax revenue from TARI grew further up to 2.9 million euros equal to an amount of 269 thousand euros equal to +10.25%. Overall, between 2010 and 2022, the value of collections connected with waste management grew by 1,630,914.90 euros, equal to a value of 128.45%. In 2010, waste management fees in Adelfia amounted to 76.98 euros, while in 2022 this value reached an amount of 175.86 euros. Waste management taxes as a percentage of total tax

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revenues in 2010 amounted to 29.81%. Subsequently, they grew to 34%. In other words, waste management taxes have grown more than tax revenues which also had an increasing trend between 2010 and 2022. If we consider management taxes as a percentage of the total collections of the municipality of Adelfia, we note that this value has gone from 12.69% in 2010 up to a value of 20.03% in 2022. In other words, tax revenues from waste management make up about 20% of the total revenue of the municipality of Adelfia in 2022. Of every euro that the municipality of Adelfia collects, about 20 cents are produced by taxes related to waste management in 2022. The total collections of the municipality of Adelfia between 2010 and 2022 grew by 44.72%, tax revenues grew by 100.28%, from waste management grew by 128.45%.

The payments of the municipality of Adelfia for waste management between 2010 and 2022. Below we consider the waste expenditure of the municipality of Adelfia between 2010 and 2022. In 2010 the municipality of Adelfia spent about 1,724. €140.22 for waste management. Between 2010 and 2011 the value of the waste management payment increased by an amount equal to €1,843,092.05 or a value equal to €118,951.83, equal to 6.90%. Between 2011 and 2012, the expenditure of the municipality of Adelfia for waste management grew up to 1,963,850.20 euros or an amount equal to 120,758.15 euros, equal to 6.55%. Between 2012 and 2013, the expenditure for waste management in the municipality of Adelfia grew by 80,131.32 euros or 4.08% up to an amount of 2,043,981.52 euros. Between 2013 and 2014, the value of waste management expenditure grew by an amount equal to 216,620.42 euros, equal to 10.60%, up to an amount of 2,260,601.94 euros. Between 2014 and 2015, the value of expenditure for waste management in the municipality of Adelfia decreased by an amount equal to 158,585.56 euros or 7.02% down to an amount of 2,102,016.38 euros. Between 2015 and 2016, the expenditure for waste management in the municipality of Adelfia decreased by an amount of 255,776.69 euros or equal to an amount of -12.17% up to an amount of 1,846,239.69 euros. Between 2016 and 2017, the value of expenditure for waste management increased by an amount of 156,198.95 euros, equal to an amount of 8.46% up to an amount of 2,002,429.64 euros. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of waste management expenditure grew from an amount equal to 36,087.33 euros up to 1.80% up to an amount of 2,038,516.97 euros. Between 2018 and 2019, the value of waste management expenditure in Adelfia grew by 22.89%, equal to an amount of 466,702.46 euros up to an amount of 2,505,219.43 euros. Between 2019 and 2020, the value of waste management expenditure in the municipality of Adelfia grew by 14,487.36 euros or 0.58% up to an amount of 2,519,706.79 euros. Between 2021 and 2022, the value of waste management expenditure in the municipality of Adelfia grew by 871,671.11 euros or 34.59% to an amount of 3,391,377.90 euros. Between 2021 and 2022, the value of waste management expenditure in the municipality of Adelfia decreased by an amount equal to 386,846.63 euros or 11.41% up to an amount of 3,004,531.27 euros. Overall, between 2010 and 2022, the value of waste management expenditure in the municipality of Adelfia grew by 74.26% or by an amount of 1,280,391.05 euros. Between 2010 and 2020, the total value of the expenses of the municipality of Adelfia grew by 40.16%. However, the growth in waste management expenses was more intense, equal to a value of 74.26%. Between 2010 and 2022, the value of waste management expenditure as a percentage of total expenditure grew from 19.53% to 24.29%. In 2020, of every euro that the municipality of Adelfia spent, approximately 24.29 cents were spent on waste management.

Differences between receipts and payments in waste management in the municipality of Adelfia. Even though the value of waste management taxes grew by 128% between 2010 and 2022, the municipality of Adelfia has lacked the balance between receipts and payments. In fact, already in the TARES management or between 2010 and 2016 the value of the difference between receipts and payments was almost always negative. Subsequently, following the introduction of the Tari in 2016, the

difference between collections and payments in waste management became efficient and remained so until 2020. Between 2020 and 2021, the collections deriving from waste taxation returned insufficient to cover the waste management expenses of the municipality of Adelfia.

Conclusions. We can note that between 2010 and 2022 the value of waste management taxes for the municipality of Adelfia grew by 128%. However, we can consider a neighboring municipality with respect to Adelfia, such as Casamassima, to verify if there are similar trends in payments and receipts. Well, we can see that even if on the one hand the waste management costs of the municipality of Casamassima grew by 50% between 2010 and 2022, on the other hand the taxes imposed on citizens for the management of taxes grew by 14, 9%. Furthermore, if we consider the per capita value of waste management taxes in 2022, we can note that while this value was equal to 156.50 euros for the municipality of Casamassima, in the case of the Municipality of Adelfia this value was equal to 175 .86 euros. We also note that in 2022 the value of waste management expenditure was approximately 3 million euros for both the municipality of Casamassima and the municipality of Adelfia even though the municipality of Adelfia has about 2,800 fewer inhabitants than the municipality of Casamassima. The data show that if the municipality of Adelfia were at least as efficient as the municipality of Casamassima then the value of the expenditure for the management of taxes of the municipality of Adelfia in 2022 should not be 3 million euros but rather around 2.5 million of Euro. From the analysis we can therefore identify a macro-trend that appears to be quite similar to the two municipalities considered, i.e. a growth trend in waste management spending. However, the municipality of Adelfia, unlike the municipality of Casamassima, has poured this growth entirely on the citizens with an increase in taxes on waste. In the municipality of Adelfia, the increase in the tax on waste was more than proportional to the growth in municipal spending on waste. In the municipality of Casamassima, the increase in the waste tax was less than proportional to the increase in waste management costs. In any case, the municipality of Adelfia spends as much as the municipality of Casamassima despite having about 2,800 fewer inhabitants.

There is therefore ample room for improvement in the financial management of waste in the municipality of Adelfia which can benefit the population by avoiding disproportionate increases in taxation.

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Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Spese e Incassi da Gestione dei Rifiuti Comune di Casamassima			
	2010	2022	%
TASSE DA GESTIONE RIFIUTI	2.627.500,71	3.019.590,47	14,92
SPESE PER LA GESTIONE DEI RIFIUTI	2.306.900,30	3.465.154,78	50,21

TARES E TARI Entrate Tributarie Totale Incassi

Comune di Adelfia

Totale Spese Rifiuti Spese Correnti Totale Pagamenti

Spese Comune di Adelfia

Comune di Adelfia Totale Spese. Fonte: Siope

Esercizio	Totale Spese Rifiuti	Spese Correnti	Totale Pagamenti
2010	1.724.140,22 €	6.602.797,79 €	8.824.967,42 €
2011	1.843.092,05 €	6.711.634,70 €	8.706.145,25 €
2012	1.963.850,20 €	7.008.843,12 €	10.376.202,13 €
2013	2.043.981,52 €	6.717.159,65 €	8.790.224,55 €
2014	2.260.601,94 €	8.004.470,63 €	9.712.825,32 €
2015	2.102.016,38 €	8.093.325,60 €	13.468.777,63 €
2016	1.846.239,69 €	7.229.847,68 €	10.996.510,19 €
2017	2.002.429,64 €	7.308.926,51 €	10.065.711,88 €
2018	2.038.516,97 €	8.477.237,12 €	12.566.889,89 €
2019	2.505.219,43 €	8.482.851,91 €	13.010.289,79 €
2020	2.519.706,79 €	8.742.339,51 €	11.749.734,24 €
2021	3.391.377,90 €	9.965.917,42 €	12.855.311,49 €
2022	3.004.531,27 €	9.364.589,05 €	12.368.924,46 €

INCASSI COMUNE DI ADELFA. FONTE: SIOPE

<i>Esercizio</i>	<i>TARES E TARI</i>	<i>Totale Entrate Tributarie</i>	<i>Totale Incassi</i>
2010	1.269.713,95 €	4.260.022,21 €	10.006.541,07 €
2011	1.698.989,87 €	7.037.185,07 €	9.400.590,28 €
2012	1.909.046,07 €	7.693.367,41 €	10.718.240,28 €
2013	1.960.787,16 €	5.768.087,13 €	8.489.857,06 €
2014	2.261.393,46 €	7.303.301,63 €	9.911.710,47 €
2015	1.333.826,42 €	6.968.036,59 €	12.429.251,55 €
2016	2.381.991,92 €	6.933.817,69 €	11.253.095,11 €
2017	2.261.024,41 €	6.926.086,41 €	10.627.821,81 €
2018	2.128.896,29 €	7.277.969,95 €	12.366.718,88 €
2019	2.679.461,74 €	7.546.811,48 €	11.997.632,09 €
2020	2.505.643,01 €	7.685.579,25 €	13.586.354,42 €
2021	2.630.899,93 €	7.959.282,13 €	12.436.703,44 €
2022	2.900.628,85 €	8.531.792,26 €	14.480.994,64 €